

Relativistic Corrections to the 1D Schrodinger Equation for the Infinite Potential Well

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In a previous note (1), we tried to develop an approach for dealing with relativistic corrections to the Schrodinger equation by considering the relativistic bound state wavefunction:

$$W_{rel}(x) = \int dp_{rel} f(p_{rel}) \exp(i p_{rel} x) \quad ((1))$$

with $p_{rel} = p/\sqrt{1-p^2/(m^2c^2)}$ where p is the nonrelativistic momentum. We then expanded ((1)) in powers of $1/m$. $W_{rel}(x)$ is a solution of a relativistic equation (not the Schrodinger equation) and so $f(p)$ is also a solution of this relativistic equation, even if p is the nonrelativistic momentum. Thus, we defined $W_{rel}(x) \approx W_{nonrel}(x) + W_1(x) + W_b(x)$. $W_b(x)$ is obtained from the expansion of ((1)) while $W_1(x)$ may be a functional correction. We then examined different relative equations (Klein-Gordon, Dirac with potentials) to find correction terms. In this note, we try to demonstrate that all $1/m$ powers of $W_b(x)$ are 0 and:

$$\int p_{rel}^2 f(p_{rel}) \exp(i p_{rel} x) dx = \text{RHS of Klein-Gordon equation} = \int p^2 f(p) \exp(i p x) dx$$

Thus, $-d^2/dx^2$ for p_{rel}^2 carries over exactly to $-d^2/dx^2$ for p^2 without any expansions.

We apply the model of (1) to the case of the Klein-Gordon equation for a particle in an infinite well. We use exact relativistic results from (2) and expand these in powers of $1/m$ and compare with the results of (1).

Relativistic Solution to a Particle in a Box with an Infinite Potential at the Walls

In (2), the solution to this problem for the Klein-Gordon equation is given by:

$$W_{rel}(x) = \sqrt{2/L} (E_p + m) / (2 \sqrt{mE_p}) \sin(px) \text{ where } pL = n\pi \quad ((2))$$

In the interior $V=0$, while the potential is infinite at the walls 0 and L .

Expanding $(E_p + m) / (2 \sqrt{mE_p})$ yields:

$$\begin{aligned} & .5 [2 + .5p^2/(m^2c^2) - 1/8 p^4/m^4 - 1/16 p^6/m^6 \dots] \{ 1 - .25p^2/m^2c^2 + 5/32 p^4/m^4 \dots \} \\ & = .5 [2 - 1/16 p^4/m^4 + \dots] \quad ((2a)) \end{aligned}$$

It may be noted that $\sin(px)$ with the condition on p is the same for the relativistic case as for the nonrelativistic one.

The energy is given by: $E = \sqrt{p^2 + m^2}$ ((3)) as listed above. One may expand this to find $1/m$ power correction terms to the nonrelativistic energy. In particular:

$$E = m[1 + .5 p^2/m^2 - 1/8 p^4/m^4 + \dots] \quad \text{Thus, } de = -1/8 p^4/m^3 \quad ((4))$$

Effect of a Fourier Transform Expansion

Consider $p_{rel} = p + g(p)$ where p is the nonrelativistic momentum and $g(p)$ some function of order $1/m$. Then:

$$\text{Let } q(p) = f(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4a))$$

$$dp_{rel} = dp + (d/dp g) dp \quad \text{and} \quad q(p_{rel}) = q(p) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} g^n / n! d^n / dp^n q$$

Then the $1/m^n$ correction is given by:

$$\int dp g^n / n! d^n / dp^n q + \int (d/dp g) dp g^{n-1} / (n-1)! d^{n-1} / dp^{n-1} q \quad ((4b))$$

$$= \int dp d/dp [g^n / n! d^{n-1} / dp^{n-1} q] = [g^n / n! d^{n-1} / dp^{n-1} q] \text{ evaluated at the endpoints}$$

Now q as given by ((4a)) contains $f(p)$ the Fourier transform. We assume this and its derivatives die down quickly to zero at \pm infinite so ((4b)) = 0.

Thus, every $1/m^n$ correction to the Fourier series expansion is 0 or:

$$W(x) = \int dp_{rel} f(p_{rel}) \exp(ip_{rel} x) = \int dp f(p) \exp(ip x) \quad ((4c))$$

It should be noted that on the RHS the nonrelativistic momentum p is used, but this is not the Schrodinger wavefunction. Rather:

$$W(x) = \text{relativistic Schrodinger equation} = W_0(x) + W_1(x) + W_2(x) + \dots$$

where we expand in powers of $1/m$. $W_0(x)$ is the Schrodinger solution, while $W(x)$ satisfies a relativistic equation like the Klein-Gordon equation.

In the Klein-Gordon equation, one has p_{rel}^2 on the RHS. This is written as $-d^2/dx^2$. What happens for the nonrelativistic case? We repeat the argument above with:

$$q(p_{rel}) = p_{rel}^2 f(p_{rel}) \exp(ip_{rel} x) \quad ((4d))$$

Then, the conclusion seems to be the same, i.e.:

$$\int dp \, p^* p f(p) \exp(i p x) = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \int dp \, p f(p) \exp(i p x)$$

$$= \int dp \, p^* p f(p) \exp(i p x) = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} [W_0(x) + W_1(x) + \dots]$$

Thus, $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ used in the relativistic case, becomes exactly $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ in the nonrelativistic one. The wavefunction, however, has corrections. A similar argument should hold for derivatives in the Dirac equation case. In previous notes, we considered cases of:

$$\int dp \, p^n f(p) \exp(i p x) \quad ((4e))$$

This is not equal to $\int dp \, p^n f(p) \exp(i p x)$ because $p^* p$ and not $p^* p^*$ is used. ((4e)), however, will cancel with other terms of $p^* p$ as was seen.

Relativistic Corrections to the Nonrelativistic Problem

In (1), we tried to develop a formalism of finding corrections to a relativistic equation by writing:

$$W_{rel} = W_0(x) + W_1(x) + W_b(x) \quad ((5))$$

Here $W_0(x)$ is the solution of the Schrodinger equation, $W_1(x)$ a functional correction and $W_b(x)$ a correction from the expansion of:

$$W_{rel} = \int dp \, f(p) \exp(i p x) \quad \text{where } p = p + \frac{1}{2} \frac{p^3}{m^2} \quad ((6))$$

From the previous section, we know that $W_b(x)$ is 0 for all orders of $1/m$.

In general $f(p)$ is a function related to the relativistic solution and so need not match a Fourier weight from the nonrelativistic result. Here we use the Klein-Gordon equation with $V=0$ in the interior. Then:

$$(e + de + m)^2 [W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + \dots] = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} [W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + \dots] \quad ((7))$$

For this problem: $2m e_0 W_i = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_i$.

This leads to correction terms which satisfy:

$$e^* e (W_0 + W_1 + \dots) + de^* de (W_0 + W_1 + \dots) + 2m(e + de)(W_0 + W_1 + \dots) + 2e de (W_0 + W_1 + \dots) = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} (W_0 + W_1 + \dots) \quad ((8))$$

At this point, δe , a correction to the energy, is unknown.

Let first consider terms of order $1/(m^*m)$ because e , the Schrodinger energy $p^*p/2m$ is of order $1/m$.

Examining ((8)) δe might be of order $1/(m^*m)$ or $1/(m^*m^*m)$

Now: $e^*e W_0 + 2m \delta e W_0 = 0$ where $e=p^*p/2m$ is a possible solution leading to:

$\delta e =$ energy shift due to relativistic correction $= -\frac{1}{8} p^*p/(m^*m)$ which is the result obtained from an expansion of the full solution result from (2).

Correction to the Wavefunction

Given the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$[E^*E - m^*m][W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + \dots] = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} [W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + \dots] \quad ((11))$$

Consider first the power $1/m^4$ and assume W_1 is nonzero. Then:

$2e_0 m W_2$ cancels with $p^*p W_2$ on the RHS

$e_0^*e_0 W_1 + 2e_0 \delta e W_0 + 2m \delta e W_1 = 0$ This leads to W_1 canceling and the equation is invalid so we assume $W_1=0$ as is the case in the relativistic expansion of the wavefunction.

Consider finding $W_2(x)$ which is taken to be of order $1/m^4$.

From $[(e_0 + \delta e + m)^2 - m^2][W_0 + W_2 + W_3]$ one finds terms of order $1/m^6$ ($1/m^4$ does not give enough information) as:

$2e_0 m W_3$ which cancels with $p^*p W_3$ on the RHS

$$e_0^*e_0 W_2 + \delta e^*\delta e W_0 + 2m \delta e W_2 = 0 \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{This yields } W_2 = -\frac{1}{32} W_0 \quad ((13))$$

This matches the result from the expansion of the relativistic wavefunction where the factor of $1/16$ was found for the $1/m^4$ result, but the first result had a factor of 2.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have used a method from (1) to calculate relativistic corrections to the energy and wavefunction for an infinite well potential. We have compared these to $1/m$ expansions of exact relativistic results from (2). In addition, we argue that $-d/dx d/dx$ for $\text{prel}^* \text{prel}$ becomes $-d/dx d/dx$ or p^*p in the nonrelativistic case by doing expansions of prel in a Fourier transform.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relativistic Corrections to the 1-D Schrodinger Equation Using Fourier Series (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Alberto, Pedro et al Relativistic Particle in a Box: Klein-Gordon versus Dirac Equations 2017 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1711.06313.pdf>